

PROSPECTS FOR USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INSURANCE SERVICES

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Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада сунъий интеллект суғурта компанияларига ўз хизматларини яхшилашга қандай ёрдам бериши кўриб чиқилган бўлиб, шунингдек, аниқ техник ҳолатлар ва анъанавий машинани ўрганиш усуллари ва генератив сунъий интеллект ўртасидаги фарқ таҳлил қилинган.

Калим сўзлар: сунъий интеллект, рақамли трансформация, суғурта хизматлари, маълумотлар ва рискларни бошқариш, суғурта саноати.

Аннотация. В этой статье рассмотрено, как ИИ помогает страховым компаниям улучшать свои услуги, а также проанализируем конкретные технические кейсы и разницу между традиционными методами машинного обучения и генеративным ИИ.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, цифровая трансформация, страховые услуги, управление данными и рисками, страховая индустрия.

Abstract. This article looks at how AI is helping insurance companies improve their services, and also analyzes specific technical cases and the difference between traditional machine learning methods and generative AI.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, digital transformation, insurance services, data and risk management, insurance industry.

With the advancement of technology, artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming a key tool in the insurance industry, transforming the processes of risk assessment, premium calculation and data processing.

Insurance is a business based on risk assessment and management. Traditionally, risk assessment relied on statistical models and manual data processing, which required significant resources and time. With the advent of AI, insurance companies have access to new tools that allow them to process huge amounts of data in real time, improve the accuracy of forecasts, and optimize processes.

Key areas of AI application in insurance include:

1. Big Data analysis for accurate risk assessment.
2. Machine learning (ML) models for predicting events and automating tasks.
3. Generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) for creating personalized offers and optimizing customer interactions.

Traditional Machine Learning Methods: Data Processing and Management

Machine learning (ML) has long been used in insurance to predict and automate tasks. Key algorithms include regression models, decision trees, and neural networks that help analyze historical data and predict future risks.

Example of using ML. One of the leading Russian insurers applies ML models to estimate the probability of an insurance event based on long-term data. These models help determine the probabilities of various outcomes and assign appropriate premiums.

Technical aspect. Gradient boosting models such as XGBoost or LightGBM are used, which are trained on customer data, their behavior, insurance claim history, and external data

(weather conditions, accident statistics, etc.). These models can take into account dozens of factors simultaneously, improving the accuracy of calculations.

Problems. Limited adaptability to new conditions and dependence on the quality of historical data. Traditional ML models often require significant efforts to prepare data and can be subject to forecast bias [1].

Where to Use Generative AI

Generative AI (GenAI), including technologies like GPT and other transformers, is the next step in the evolution of artificial intelligence. In insurance, GenAI is used to create more personalized offers, automate customer interactions, and streamline claims processing.

GenAI use case: A European insurance company uses generative models to automate claims processing. The customer uploads photos of damage, and GenAI analyzes the images, compares them with thousands of other cases, and automatically offers a preliminary estimate of the loss.

Technical aspect: It uses neural network-based computer vision models such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), as well as language models such as GPT, to understand and analyze the text of claims. The process uses reinforcement learning to improve the quality of assessments based on feedback from experts.

How to Automate Risk Management

AI is also actively used to automate risk management, which helps insurers make more informed decisions based on data. With the help of AI, it is possible to identify hidden risks that traditional methods might miss.

AI use case: Large international insurance companies use complex risk models that include both structured (financial data, payment history) and unstructured data (social networks, news). AI analyzes the entire array of information to identify potential threats in real time.

Technical aspect: Risk models include Bayesian Networks for probabilistic analysis, as well as multi-layer neural networks to find relationships between heterogeneous data. Sensitivity analysis of models is also used to test the robustness of decisions to various scenarios.

Benefits and challenges of implementing AI

1. Accuracy and speed: AI models are able to analyze large amounts of data in a fraction of a second, which allows for faster and more accurate decision making.

2. Cost reduction: automation of routine tasks and reduction of errors allow companies to save significant resources.

3. Flexibility: generative AI allows for adaptation to changes in data and continuous learning from new examples, improving the quality of forecasts and decisions.

The main challenges include the following.

- **Data quality:** The success of AI is highly dependent on the quality and relevance of the data. Errors in the data can lead to incorrect predictions.

- **Regulatory barriers:** In some countries, the use of AI in insurance is limited by regulatory requirements, which makes it difficult to implement innovations.

- **Ethical issues:** The use of AI for risk assessment is associated with privacy and personal data protection issues [2].

The use of AI in the insurance industry opens up new opportunities to automate and improve the accuracy of risk assessment and premium calculation processes. Generative models, supplemented by traditional machine learning methods, can create new levels of personalization and efficiency. However, successful implementation requires attention to data quality, regulatory compliance, and addressing the ethical issues associated with the use of AI.

Companies that can overcome these challenges will benefit by offering customers more reliable and personalized insurance products that are ready for the challenges of the new era.

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